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Research Article

**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COLLECTIVE
ENDOWMENT PAPERS AND THE IRANIAN ECONOMY:
CASE OF ENDOWMENT AND CHARITY AFFAIRS
ORGANIZATION**Saeideh Rezaei¹ and Iman Jokar^{2*}¹ Department of Management, Marvdasht Branch, Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Iran^{2*} Department of Management, Shiraz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Shiraz, Iran**Abstract:**

The main objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between bonds of mass devoted to Iran's macroeconomic indicators (including economic growth, employment and investments) respectively. To achieve this aim, a questionnaire in relation to the three macro-economic variables include: 1. Economic growth 2. Unemployment 3. The investment was designed. To assess the reliability and validity of the questionnaire was approved by Cronbach's alpha coefficient has-been The rate for the entire questionnaire obtained 0.77 and this number is indicative of the extent appropriate and acceptable reliability. The population consisted of professors and economic elite, familiar with the field of endowment management and financial management and organization at the University endowments are in Fars Province This number has been estimated that about 58 people. Considering the population size of the sample using a sample of 50 people. In this study, a questionnaire was distributed among all members of society, and finally 50 questionnaires (to the participants) were returned The sampling method in this research is available sampling method. To assess data normality Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess the association of papers devoted to collective direction With macroeconomic indicators at 95% single sample t-test was used, The results revealed a significant positive correlation between bond is endowed with three macroeconomic variables. The bonds can be devoted to economic recovery in the variables of economic growth, unemployment and investment foundations.

Keywords: Dedicated, devoted to collective security, economic growth, unemployment, investment**Corresponding author:**

Iman Jokar,
Department of Management,
Marvdasht Branch, Islamic Azad University,
Marvdasht,
Iran,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the first organizations of civil financial endowment in Islamic society. The endowment was established during the lifetime of the Prophet. The aim of devoting the first day for the poor, the helpless, the way of Allah and every type of service to the public And with the aim of closeness to God and respond to the problems of the day and mostly positive role in society. In addition to religious places such as mosques, shrines and tombs, endowment widespread and has taken a significant role in other areas of society Such as the establishment of hospitals, educational centers, libraries, inn, water storage, helping the poor classes of society or environmental objectives Although this institution was always as a non-governmental entity, but under the influence of multiple periods of Governors and the state. Development of endowment functions of political development, economic and social Muslim community. for an endowment and charity are, however, legal and regulatory obstacles and the lack of appropriate cultural and legal contexts, the endowment is limited (Ebadi, 2008). Such as the establishment of hospitals, educational centers, libraries, inn, water storage, helping the poor classes of society or environmental objectives although this institution was always as a non-governmental organization, But under the influence of multiple periods of Governors and the state. Development of endowment functions of political development, economic and social Muslim community. With the dedication of little lasting legacy is still widespread, Unfortunately, staying trapped in old structures and the changing financial laws and regulations dedicated Consecrated in some countries has led to the development of new financial endowment in line with financial capacities for an endowment and charity not be there today, However, the legal and regulatory obstacles and the lack of appropriate cultural and legal contexts, the endowment is limited (Ebadi, 2008). Therefore, the use of new methods for strengthening a culture of dedication to the community and to create appropriate platforms Various sectors of society to participate in the good tradition of endowment and charity are needed more than ever So as to keep pace with culturally appropriate context to study the socio-economic and cultural benefits of good practice, The new capacity created through the operation. In this regard, endowments and charitable action devoted to the publication of the first papers In March 2013 order to build hospitals and to the beginning of the Cancer Research Centre Great for a change in the structure of the endowment, economic and social effects as well as benefit from it.

Importance and necessity of research

There are several ways to do good deeds and pious, one of the most enduring is dedicating methods.

People in the form devoted part of their assets (such as land, houses, gardens, etc.) account for philanthropic purposes according to the needs of society. With an overview of the Dedicated to the history we can see that this good tradition has always different levels of cultural, social and economic respectively. The development of major scientific centers and universities, including socio-cultural work is dedicated. In addition, from the social point of view, the government seriously interested in the involvement of people in this area is They alone are not able to solve all social problems and poverty elimination and economic sphere also been dedicated to preventing the accumulation of wealth And with the support of many endowments wheels in motion comes from economic centers. Islam has devoted special attention to. Today, with the establishment of endowed institutions in developed countries, the issue of investment in endowment value and positive place to be allocated. But in Islamic countries, including Iran, for reasons such as incompatibility imagine this kind of investment and legal foundations of Islamic law and the lack of appropriate legal, So far, there has been tangible progress in this area (Soroush, 2013). Careful examination of the nature of the functions and endow indicate favorable effects on society, including its dedication these cases can be noted: Social Security needs of the poor classes of society, Make scientific support and education dedicated to schools, libraries, etc., suppliers, improving religious worship and the needs of society, such as the creation of the hospital and ... (Ebadi, 2008).

BACKGROUND RESEARCH:**Internal records**

Safai Pour et al (2013) in his review as "endowment effect on economic development in Ahvaz," writes Endowment is always a means to resolve economic and social problems, including the fight against poverty, welfare and so was considered. Islamic civilization owes the public endowments in the history of Islam. Endowment can be invested in public works related to security purpose, spirituality, Economic growth and justice that have special significance in Islamic economics to the accumulation of physical and human capital and thus contribute to the general welfare of the Islamic world. Endowment very important factor in preventing the concentration and centralization of wealth in the society. Ebrahimi Salari and colleagues (2012) in a research entitled "Investigation of money devoted to legal and economic effects with emphasis on poverty and employment" wrote: endowment money very important factor in preventing the accumulation of wealth in society and a factor for economic justice and social And has a great impact in reducing the gap. In religious culture, consecrated in poverty is

the opposite. So spread the endowment money is an important factor in reducing the level of poverty in the community. Because with the loss of wealth accumulation, capital placed at the disposal of and benefit from the amenities, Evolution in all aspects. Also, the endowment provides an important role in the development of jobs in the community.

Sayah et al (2009) study entitled "Feasibility dedicated stocks and funds, endowment fund shares and money in the Iranian model" of the legal framework and jurisprudence are looking for dedicated stocks and money, then the dynamic model of an institution efficient dedication has paid simultaneously to maximize wealth (donor) and optimize the resource allocation process help. Salimifar (2008) in his review as "consecrated ground for economic development," says historical evidence suggests that the endowment central role in the development of various aspects of educational, social and economic is played. Saleh Abadi (2007) of "dedicated stocks of Islam" On the possibility of devoting Company's stock; in this article, the stock corporation as a legal fact and phenomenon are the property of and ability to find their endowment. In other words, people started buying shares of companies that are dedicated to their benefits they are dedicated to their benefits In many ways, but in the securities charity dedicated to all aspects of securities does not have to be defined for specific projects. Dadgar et al (2007) in a research entitled "Feasibility devoted to money-tool in the development of literature and economic activity" wrote: Religious culture is devoted to just the opposite of poverty. With the expansion of the money dedicated to poverty and deprivation in society is reduced, because as mentioned endowment is one way to prevent the accumulation of wealth. With the accumulation of wealth, social capital will be available to everyone, and enjoy all the amenities and economic development in the fields of cultural, political and social displacement.

Foreign backgrounds

Ibrahim Ahmed et al (2014) in their study titled "dedicated asset management in Kuwait and Egypt," wrote Kuwait's endowment in relation to income distribution income and interest consecrated in Kuwait in the way of social services including health development, support students to cover the cost of tuition And other educational expenses as well as the development of social and economic infrastructure And scientific projects to promote scientific, cultural and social development Through a combination of activities and ventures dedicated government seems to consumption. Cajee (2007), "restore the endowment in developing countries" to review and says stakeholders dedicated not only to Muslim countries and religious activities are not limited to, But also the broader activities covering the main objective of Improve and strengthen the social and economic

development of a country. Abdol Karim (2007) in an article titled "Management and development of the contemporary consecrated in Singapore: Challenges and Perspectives," to develop assets dedicated to providing solutions, one of which is dedicated to cash. In this way, people are divided into different income groups and each group is a maximum amount of that income increases Allocated to finance public-benefit activities. Ahmed (2007) in an article entitled "microfinance-based endowment: the realization of the social role of Islamic finance" has proposed an institutional design that is a source of endowment funds; In this way, the same dedicated focus on stability and for recommending that the property mentioned in activities with Less investment risk so that the original devote resources remain constant. Ahmed (2004) in his article " Dedicated role in reducing the risk of poverty " Noted that all the people may not have the financial capability required to dedicate land or buildings. Noted that all the people may not have the financial capability required to dedicate land or buildings.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

According to the research community dedicated to explain the relationship bond with the economy, The method used for this research is descriptive survey. In this method selection and the selected sample of the population and using statistical methods such as Cronbach's alpha results are reviewed. Descriptive studies are both practical and fundamental aspects in applied dimension Descriptive studies are both practical and fundamental aspects in applied dimension Research carried out according to two methods can be divided criterion of objective research and data collection. The aim of this research in terms of basic research is theoretical.

Statistical Society

The population is defined as a collection of individuals or units that have at least one common trait (khaki, 2007). The study population consisted of experts and professors of economics, management and financial management in universities and the National Endowment familiar with the field of endowment and charity affairs Fars province On the basis of population size was estimated to be about 58 people.

Sample

In this study, the number of samples obtained using a sample of 50 people And sampling method Sampling method is available.

Methods of data collection

The phenomenon of quantitative and qualitative features that awareness about these features in nature, and is dependent on achieving them. This phenomena as the variables are evolving over time. The aim of the research such as descriptive or explanatory, access to information about the

changes. Find answers and solutions to the problem of selection in each study involves gaining access to the data is Through which we can make hypotheses as possible answers have been researched and tested for solving temporary (khaki, 2007).

To collect the data, two general methods have been used:

1. The library method: study books, articles and national and international journals related to the topic Research

2-way field: Questionnaires

Data analysis tools

SPSS software to analyze the data, the data were transmitted to a computer. Data analysis was conducted in two parts. In the first part using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables and distributional indexes to describe the sample population studied. In the second part using inferential statistics such as t-test hypotheses research.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to gender index

Percent Of valid responses	Percent of the total	Number	Gender
74	74	37	Man
26	26	13	Female
-	0	0	Unanswered
100	100	50	Total

Table 2: Results Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

investment	Unemployment	Economic Growth	Bonds of mass devoted	Variables Indicators
1.268	3.097	2.143	2.231	Kolmogorov-Smirnov
0.08	0.078	0.082	0.98	The significance level

First hypothesis: the issuance of collective endowment and economic growth there is a significant relationship To test the first hypothesis univariate t-test was used.

Table 3: single-sample t-test for components of economic growth

Sig	df	Standard deviation	Average	Maximum	At least	Variable name
0.001	49	2.288	11.52	15	3	Economic Growth

$$H_0 = \mu = 9$$

$$H_1 = \mu \neq 9$$

The second hypothesis: the issuance of collective dedication and reduce unemployment there is a significant relationship.

To test the first hypothesis univariate t-test was used.

Table 4: one-sample t-test for components to reduce unemployment

Sig	df	Standard deviation	Average	Maximum	At least	Variable name
0.001	49	2.225	11.9	15	3	Reducing unemployment

$$H_0 = \mu = 9$$

$$H_1 = \mu \neq 9$$

The third sub-hypothesis: the issuance of collective endowment and increased investment, there is a significant relationship.

The third hypothesis to test one sample t-test was used.

Table 5: one-sample t-test for increased investment component

Sig	df	Standard deviation	Average	Maximum	At least	Variable name
0.001	49	3.145	13.84	20	4	Increased investment

$$H_0 = \mu = 12$$

$$H_1 = \mu \neq 12$$

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

First hypothesis: the issuance of collective dedicated to economic growth and there is a According to the results of . Significant correlation t-test, the issuance of collective dedicated to economic growth and There is a significant positive

It can be inferred that directs funds .relationship collected Through the papers devoted to the creation of micro and macro-economic units and services In the community can the increase in gross domestic product and provide the internal Conditions through the identification and the possible use of vacant capacity in the economy Needed to achieve the economic growth. The

results for this hypothesis with the results of the Jahanian (2010) is consistent. The second hypothesis: the issuance of collective endowment and unemployment and there is a significant correlation. The results of t-test showed that there is a significant positive correlation between bonds and variable dedicated to reducing unemployment. It can be concluded that if proper management The collected papers and guiding investment to create economic units and services can be created by increasing the number of businesses And the subsequent increase in demand for labor, in order to reduce unemployment in the community reinvigorated movement of jobs to applicants as well as lending facility (of the collected funds) to create micro-businesses can A big step to reducing unemployment in the community. For people with intellectual capital necessary to create a firm or an industry has been created and several people can be entrepreneurs and to entrench sometimes due to a lack of capital and funding Why cannot borrow money from banks that have loans from banks require collateral, and because they are not able to

provide collateral cannot be active in this field. The results of the second hypothesis democracy and Seyyed Hosseini and Ebrahimi similarallari results (2012) is. The third sub-hypothesis: the issuance of collective dedicated to increasing investment and there is a significant correlation. According to the third hypothesis can be confirmed It is understood that the bonds of mass dedicated to collect funds through micro and macro in the hands of people can While enabling the accumulation of capital and increasing domestic investment in the country, along with the creation of centers and social and economic infrastructure (which makes it possible to provide essential services and living standards) The location of these assets, the background necessary to increase foreign investment in the country to provide it. As well as the use of funds collected by these bonds to build centers and manufacturing and service firms and infrastructure needed community can A substantial contribution to improving the business climate in the country play. Average society to measure a substantial contribution to improving the business climate in the country play. The average community dedicated to evaluating its relationship with increased investment securities (13.84) was higher than the average of other variables, And this could indicate that the majority of the population of issuance devote a significant contribution in increasing investment in the country It can be extended with the use of these bonds as a new way of financing, The increase provides more investment in the country and the community will benefit from its positive consequences. The results for the fourth hypothesis with the results Abdo Tabrizi (1999) is consistent.

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